

Global Warming Operating Hypothesis for a Trend Reversal

Roberto Brusa
High School Diploma

Mechanical Expert Chief Technician
Olgiate Olona, Varese, ITALY

Abstract:- Purpose of this work is to present the arguments that are the basic ideas for an operating solution to global warming problem.

Keywords:- *Essential, Harmony, Mirror, Sacrifice, Seed, Sustainability, Thanksgiving.*

I. INTRODUCTION

I would like to spend some personal considerations that are the basis of all this work.

This research began when driving one of my first cars on a hot summer afternoon in 1970.

A boiling problem forced me to stop to cool the engine. Youthful impatience made me open the radiator cup too early, causing me a painful burn.

Instantly and without premeditation, an intuition took shape in my mind: “Are we crazy? Are we going around with a fire lit even in summer? “

Everything started at that moment, 52 years ago. Today I can say that that intuition would have been the doubt that a Wise person would have made about the sustainability of what we call progress, linked to our lifestyle.

Since every kind of Energy at the end is transformed into Heat, apparently it looks like a problem without solution.

In the history of our living Planet, we find past cycles of warming and glaciations, showing instead this possibility.

Also in our recent history, humanity lived in a period where the Oceans temperature, after a first increase in 1910, had a small reduction between 1940 and 1965, before increase again from 1965 up to now.

In [2] I recognize the request of proposed solutions, and this is my contribute.

II. METHOD

In 1973 when I obtained my high school diploma, I remember that the scientific community was debating whether from a thermodynamic point of view the Earth should be considered an opened or closed system, i.e., whether there was a possibility of an exchange of heat/energy with empty space.

Today’s situation shows that the EARTH must be considered a closed system, apart from the so-called Albedo effect, i.e., the ability to reflect incoming light energy, from and into space.

The Terrestrial Vegetable kingdom uses the Energy of Light coming from the SUN, transforming it into Matter, absorbing Carbon Dioxide emission, and producing Oxygen through an endothermic process, supplying the Animal Kingdom with the food necessary for survival.

This also happens in environments with salt and sweet waters, showing us what is considered the Miracle of Life, expressed in [7] with the concept of Sacredness of Matter.

Between 1712 and 2022, we introduced into the environment a Total Energy of approximately 735Gtoe, or 29,2kQuadBTU, equivalent to 30.8ZJ [5].

The problem that we must (try to) solve, can be conceptually summarized as follows: Being able to transfer the Energy accumulated on the Earth into Space, without reducing the Total amount of Energy coming from the Sun, an Indispensable Condition for the Survival of every form of Life.

III. DISCUSSION

From more than three years now, I have been connecting with the ISS to observe the Earth from a point of view located approximately at 400km Above Sea Level, and when something arouses my curiosity, taking advantage of the possibilities available, I take photos or videos.

Looking at a night photo taken with the ISS SD Camera, which offers a perpendicular view of the Horizon, I noticed two things.

The first was a curve parallel to the surface of the EARTH, which with the help of friends and CAD systems we were able to quantify in 80km, corresponding to the upper limit of Mesosphere, errors excepted.

Making a color print of the image with my printer, I was amazed to see that above this curve (spherical surface) there is nothing but Empty Dark Space.

This effect, magnified by the lack of color in the printer, proved me that energy is trapped beneath this surface.

Second, it was the lights that come from the cities during the night shoot, and that triggered the idea for me, which I am going to develop in this research.

Everyone knows or perceives that Light is Heat, and that Light can travel in empty Space without cooling down, the so-called Solar Radiation, and that this Radiation is ESSENTIAL for the sustainability of whole organisms.

On Earth there are areas such the Deserts or the top of Mountains for example, where the presence of Life seems to be more reduced.

The working hypothesis could initially consist of a simulation program which, considering the installations of Mirrors or White panels perpendicular to Earth's Radius, makes it possible to calculate the amount of Solar Energy that we can reflect into Space, interfering as less as possible with the other Vital Processes because installations are made in Desert areas.

Naturally, the annual reduction of Energy consumption is also to be considered ESSENTIAL, because it represents the origin of the current situation.

Both these two actions represent in my opinion the concept of Sacrifice [6], in other words the New Globally Sustainable Lifestyle.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This is only 1/8G points of view and may be or not the solution of our problem.

What I want to point out is that we need each other's.

I can explain the idea, but I cannot neither make a software program to test the validity, nor to build the Mirrors and install them.

It is the Global Lifestyle that can solve the problem using less Energy as possible, like during a War but not because of it.

In [4] is reported an apologue connected with mirroring concept.

We must stay concentrate on our surviving problems, with less emotional circuits as possible [3], and above all we need to have a farsighted DESIGN [8], representing the HOPE for Surviving.

In some populations, when they collect food in Nature for their Surviving, they used to leave something from themselves as a Sign of Gratitude and Forgiving.

I feel that the main thing that our Culture has forgotten is to give back whatever we take if we want to have Future for next generations.

To say the same concept in other words: Give back to the Universe all the Energy that we produce, like a Thanksgiving

Prayer, with a double installation of Solar panels producing Energy plus Mirrors that reflect into Space the same amount of Energy we need.

Somebody think that we must leave the Planet better than we were born, one of the main meanings of existence.

The need to operate in global agreement, in a regime of Harmony and Peace is ESSENTIAL.

We need all the people, because the work to be done will be immense: it will be much more manual, reducing the use of Energy.

We need to bring the ratio between the mass of water and ICE [5], back to a safe zone, i.e., around 1900, to have a margin of maneuver of at least five generations, necessary in my opinion to keep alive the Sensitivity regarding Climate Topic, guaranteeing its generational transmission through constant updating.

Constant updating for all generations becomes ESSENTIAL, because we absolutely need whole people with their single personality: children, teenagers, parents, grandparents and more, to arrive at HARMONY in global choices, an ESSENTIAL condition for a conscious and lasting PEACE.

I consider Thoughts, Intuitions, Dreams like Seeds, and in [1] there is a very power concept:

“And one is forced to reflect on the invisible power of the creative energy hidden in the seeds”.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Agostino d'Ipbona, (2010), PENSIERI a cura di Carlo Cremona, 585-p 248, II edizione Tascabili Bompiani, Milano
- [2]. Corinne Le Quèrè, (2022), Confession of a Climate Scientist, <https://youtu.be/abhSpr-TqFs>
- [3]. Daniela Lucangeli, (2017), Emotional short-circuits: the intelligence behind mistakes, <https://youtu.be/QuC52loTczY>
- [4]. Eva de Vitray-Meyerovitch, (1991), I MISTICI DELL'ISLAM Antologia del sufismo, p 33-34, Ugo Guanda Editore, Parma
- [5]. IJISRT22SEP618, (2022), Global Warming Analysis Upgrading Cross Check and Opened Questions, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7160671>
- [6]. Raimon Panikkar, (2019), I VEDA MANTRAMANJARI a cura di Milena Carrara Pavan, BUR Rizzoli, Mondadori Libri S.p.A. Milano
- [7]. Raimon Panikkar, (2011), Sacralità materia e vita, https://youtu.be/y_JTn_9NV9k
- [8]. Ronald Shakespear, (2013), Nunca pidas permiso, <https://youtu.be/EFdEmbuikOW>